

European Public Local Authorities' Network for
driving the Energy Transition

D7.6 - Communication and Dissemination activities report

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Executive Summary

ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action cofounded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. ePLANET aims to deploy a new clustering governance for energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonised information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

This document is the second release of ePLANET's Communication and Dissemination (C&D) activities report, which summarises the C&D activity of the project until M24. This document is developed as an intermediate report to validate the progress of the C&D activities within the two first years of the project.

A final release will be elaborated by the end of the project with the complete three year C&D activities report.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
CA	Consortium Agreement
CMP	Communication and Dissemination Plan
CoM	Covenant of Mayors
ESCO	Energy Services Companies
ET	Energy Transition
ETM	Energy Transition Measures
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
MoA	Memorandum of Adhesion
PA	Public Authority
PP	Project partner
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SEAP	Sustainable Energy Action Plan
SECAP	Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan
TG	Target Groups
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The first version of the Communication and Dissemination activities of ePLANET project are defined in the Communication and Dissemination Plan (Deliverable D7.1), which is part of Work Package 7. This WP centralises the majority of ePLANET's communication and dissemination activities. Work Package 7 consists of different tasks:

- T7.1: Communication and Dissemination plan and coordination
- T7.2: Visual identity
- T7.3: Project website
- T7.4: Promotional material
- T7.5: Conferences
- T7.6: Social media
- T7.7: Newsletters and press releases
- T7.8: Final event

The “Communication and Dissemination Activities report” analyses the progress of all C&D activities performed by project partners until M24, contributing to guarantee the proposed communication and dissemination strategy is effectively implemented.

This document will also support the elaboration of the updated Communication and Dissemination Plan (CMP), expected by M28.

2 Communication and Dissemination plan

2.1 Communication and Dissemination objectives

All the communication and dissemination activities have been designed to have an impact on the specific segmented target audiences of the project. The main objectives of communication and dissemination activities are:

- Guaranteeing the scientific and public coverage of the project results.
- Supporting optimal conditions and solutions for replicating and exploiting the project outcomes.
- Consolidating the project visibility among public authorities and stakeholders at EU level to enhance awareness.

These objectives are closely related with European “Communication EU research and innovation guidance for project participants” handbook, which highlights the need to communicate the benefits of EU funded projects to the whole society.

2.2 Communication and Dissemination strategy and KPIs

Different channels have been defined in CMP, to maximise the communication and dissemination of the project’s outputs. The proposed channels can be grouped into 8 categories:

- Website
- Social networks, in particular LinkedIn, Twitter and Youtube.
- Press releases and newsletters
- Stakeholders Forum
- Webinars and workshops
- Videos
- Conferences and scientific publications
- Site visits

It’s important to evaluate the audience that has been reached by the project, both in quantitative and qualitative parameters. The reactions caused by the project and the audience’s satisfaction level are important to focus the following communication actions better.

Next tables include the means of evaluation of the different communication and dissemination activities. The related KPIs are the objectives at the end of the project.

Table 2-1: Communication activities KPIs

COMMUNICATION AREA	KPIs	Expected value at M36
PROJECT WEBSITE	Number of unique visitors (Google Analytics)	4000
	Number of visits (monthly average) (Google Analytics)	100
TWITTER	Number of followers	500
	Number of impressions	+10.000
LINKEDIN	Number of members	500
	Number of shares	+300
YOUTUBE	Institutional video - number of views	1000
	Regional videos (explaining project) - total views	1500
	EU-wide videos - number of total views	1000
NEWSLETTER	Number of publications	6
PRESS RELEASES	Number of press-releases	16

Table 2-2: Dissemination activities KPIs

DISSEMINATION AREA	KPIs	Expected value at M36
STAKEHOLDERS FORUM	Engaged stakeholders	150
WEBINARS & WORKSHOPS	Number of attendees (total) in:	
	User empowerment private webinars	960
	User empowerment public webinars	720
	User empowerment private workshops	240
	Scaling-up webinars	720
	Scaling-up workshops	120
CONFERENCES & EVENTS	Number of attendees (total) in:	
	Presentation to conferences	320
	Final event	50
SITE VISITS	Number of attendees (total)	75

3 Detailed KPIs analysis per activity

The description of the different Communication and Dissemination activities performed in the framework of the project has already been presented in the different releases of the “Communication and Dissemination Plan”.

This section includes the relevant information regarding the progress of the key performance indicators for each of the activities, the estimation of the indicators by the end of the project as well as some additional information regarding the activities undergone during last months.

3.1 Project website

The project website has been created following the planned timeline. It’s available at www.eplaneth2020.eu. The ePLANET website has been designed to be user-friendly and easy to use, with a smooth transition between the different sections and some transversal functionalities (e.g. social networks, contact form, subscription to newsletter, news, languages) that are present in different sections.

The website has been continuously updated with all de public deliverables already submitted, the specific sections for the Open Call for follower regions and more than 30 news.

Figure 3-1 - “News” section (partial view)

KPIs analysis

Next table shows the evolution of the main performance indicators until M24, and the expected values if the 2nd year trend is maintained in the 3rd one.

Table 3-1: website KPIs evolution and M36 estimation following 2nd year trend

KPIs	GA	M12	M18	M24	expected M36
# unique visitors	4000	719	1962	2866	>4000
# visits, monthly average	100	82	109	336	>100

It is increasingly difficult to maintain the ratio of new visitors to the website, but we consider that at M36 we will be aligned with the proposed GA value. Regarding the monthly average number of visits, it is above expectations, and we expect to continue with this positive trend until the end of the project.

It is interesting to mention that these values do not consider project partners' own activity related to the ePLANET project. In particular, the different ePLANET activities performed by project partners (website news, newsletters, mailings, etc.) have had an audience of more than 17.400 people by M24.

3.2 Social networks

Specific ePLANET accounts have been created in Twitter and LinkedIn social networks, to inform about the project events, developments, and achievements.

More than 65 publications in LinkedIn and 80 short news in Twitter have been published until M24, most of them within the 2nd year of the project. Considering both accounts, the ePLANET project is followed by more than 649 followers.

A Youtube channel has also been created to share the different videos that will be elaborated within the project. At M24 (with only 1 video published), the Youtube channel has 72 subscribers.

The reach of these channels is very relevant. Compared to the initial estimation on Twitter channel (10.000 impressions), the activity of ePLANET within Twitter has had a total reach of more than 21.250 impressions at the end of the 2nd year. Moreover, the reach of LinkedIn account (even if not included as a KPI in the GA) is also very high, with more than 12.200 impressions.

ePlanetH2020
263 followers
1w • 🌐

Some progress has been made lately in the deployment of the ePLANET platform in the pilot regions of ePLANET project.

🌱 In Girona region (Catalonia), the ePLANET team has started the process to connect the ePLANET platform to DATADIS. DATADIS, a platform with data about electricity consumption, will create one unique user to access all the Girona Province required information.

Besides, our technical team is working on the interaction with the SomComunitat tool in order to be able to make the first sizing of an Energy Community using the public roofs for the PV installation to automatize the calculation of the SECAP template data.

🌱 Furthermore, the ePLANET team has finalised to gather all the energy consumption data from the buildings in Zlin region (Czech Republic) and Crete region (Greece), and this week it will finalise to upload all the energy efficiency measures data from the buildings in Zlin region into the platform. This will allow to further demonstrate the ePLANET Use Case 2 (management of energy consumption from buildings and assessment of energy efficiency measures made within them).

We will keep you informed with further updates! 🌱

ePlanetH2020
263 followers
1mo • 🌐

Launching the testing period of the ePLANET platform in Crete!

The cycle of ePLANET Capacity Building Activities in Crete progresses following the expected planning. From Monday July 10th to Wednesday July 12th 2023, the RDFC (Regional Development Fund of Crete) organized 3 extra workshops following the launching of the testing of ePLANET platform. Most of the workshops were hybrid, with CIMNE and CRES providing extra guidance and clarification online.

Each day was devoted to a different municipality. The 1st day the workshop was held at Ierapetra municipality, including discussion with the municipal energy teams. 2nd day at Rethymno municipality and 3rd day at municipality of Agios Nikolaos.

From the fruitful discussion with the technical municipal staff very interesting results were drawn for additional adjustments which would facilitate not only the use of the platform but also an integrated digitalized process for the energy transition of the municipalities.

The need for a delegated municipal officer fully devoted to the management of sustainable energy transition plans and projects had been also identified as one of the critical points. Participants suggested that such an organizational structure should also be accompanied with the hiring of additional highly qualified personnel.

During August, our Capacity Building Activities will take a break. We will resume it on September and it will last until the 1st quarter of 2024. Don't hesitate to follow us on LinkedIn and Twitter, or to subscribe to our ePLANET newsletter to be updated with our latest news.

[#energyTransition](#) [#governance](#) [#digitalisation](#) [Covenant of Mayors - Europe](#)
[CINEA - European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency](#)

ePlanetH2020
263 followers
2mo • 🌐

🗨️ Last week, we organised some [#CapacityBuilding](#) [#workshops](#) in Chania (Crete Island)!

🏠 On the 1st workshop, we supported Chania, Platania and Kantanou-Selinou in how to improve [#EnergyTransition](#) in their municipalities.

🏠 On the 2nd day of our cycle of [#CapacityBuilding](#) [#workshops](#) we worked with Minoa Pediadas, Viannos and Arhanes-Asterousia local authorities to enhance their Energy Transition [#governance](#)

[#harmonisation](#) [#platform](#) [#energy](#) [#H2020](#) [#HorizonEurope](#)

[CINEA - European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency](#)
[Covenant of Mayors - Europe](#)

Figure 3-2 - examples of LinkedIn posts published between M18 and M24

ePlanet @ePlanetH2020 · Aug 2
 Happy to announce that our 6th press release is out!

We discuss the topic **#clusteringgovernance** and we highlight which are the principles of this approach and how it can enhance current governance practices.

Full article [+](https://lnkd.in/d/P879uZS)
lnkd.in/d/P879uZS

#H2020 #EUproject #energy

4 retweets, 4 likes, 100 views

ePlanet @ePlanetH2020 · Jul 26
 ePLANET will deliver 24 capacity building activities targeting more than 900 public authorities in pilot regions.

Key findings of the needs-assessment:

- Primary barriers: lack of technical expertise
- Need of financial support
- Most relevant sectors: buildings and **#solarenergy**

2 retweets, 5 likes, 58 views

ePlanet @ePlanetH2020 · Jul 18
 Launching the testing period of **#ePLANET** platform in Crete!

The cycle of Capacity Building Activities in **#Crete** started with 3 extra workshops. Most of the workshops in Ierapetra, Rethymno and Agios Nikolaos municipalities. In August, we will take a break, but will resume on Sept.

2 retweets, 6 likes, 297 views

ePlanet @ePlanetH2020 · Jun 9
 Now starting the 2nd day of our cycle of **#CapacityBuilding** **#workshops** in Crete Islands.

today we're working with Minoa Pediadas, Viannos and Arhanes-Asterousia local authorities to enhance their **#EnergyTransition** **#governance**

#harmonisation **#platform** @cinea_eu @eumayors

4 retweets, 8 likes, 172 views

ePlanet @ePlanetH2020 · Jul 6
 ePLANET platform aims to achieve a harmonized data sharing by different actions, one of them, the digitalisation of SECAPs by monitoring the progress of **#energytransition** plans by administrations to specify and update the status of completion of their planned ET measures.

Energy balance dashboard showing 'Projected monthly electricity consumption (2020 - 2021)'. The chart displays consumption in GWh for each month from January to December. Values range from 0.8 to 1.6 GWh.

Month	Consumption (GWh)
January	1.5
February	1.3
March	1.2
April	1.1
May	0.9
June	1.2
July	1.6
August	1.5
September	1.4
October	1.4
November	0.8
December	1.5

4 retweets, 8 likes, 172 views

Figure 3-3 - examples of Twitter posts published between M18-M24

KPIs analysis

Next table shows the evolution of the GA KPIs until M24, and the expected values at M36 if the 2nd year trend is maintained in the 3rd one.

Table 3-2: social accounts KPIs evolution and M36 estimation following 2nd year trend

KPIs	GA	M12	M18	M24	expected M36
# twitter followers	500	194	236	387	>500
# twitter impressions	10000	8358	15582	21272	>30000
# LinkedIn members	500	126	217	262	400
# LinkedIn shares	300	25	79	155	285

As shown in the table above, the performance of the Twitter account is above expectations. It will be necessary to keep the 2nd year trend, which doesn't represent any significant issue.

Concerning the LinkedIn account, action is required to grant the GA expectations. The 2nd year trend has been very positive and represents a very significant improvement compared to the 1st year results. However, some improvements need to be deployed for the 3rd year to achieve the project expectations. The project team is already working on the strategy for the final year, which will be described in the next Communication and Dissemination Plan. In any case, the proposed actions do not represent any major difficulties, and so the ePLANET team considers that the GA values will be achieved by the end of the project.

3.3 Newsletter and Press releases

Press Releases

The publication of press releases is following the proposed planning, with 6 press releases published until M24 (see next table).

Table 3-3: press releases calendar

#	date	Thematic area
1	sep-21	Project launch
2	dec-21	Project moves forward
3	dec-22	Stakeholders Forum
4	jan-23	Follower Regions
5	mar-23	Half of project summary
6	may-23	Governance
7	sep-23	Capacity Building

8	oct-23	Platform
9	nov-23	Case Studies
10	dec-23	Follower Regions & Joint-exchange activities
11	jan-24	EU-wide replicability
12	feb-24	Last semester of the project
13	apr-24	Webinars & workshops (?)
14	may-24	SF (?)
15	jun-24	Platform & Tools
16	aug-24	ePLANET in a nutshell

During the 3rd year of the project, 10 more press releases will be published. The thematic area for almost all of them is already defined, even if the calendar can be modified according to the progress of the different technical achievements.

The current number of subscriptions to the newsletter being small, the newsletter has also been directly distributed to the project partners (to include it on their own newsletters) as well as through LinkedIn, Twitter and the project website.

Figure 3-4 - examples of Press Releases published between M18-M24

Newsletter

The publication of the digital ePLANET newsletter follows the proposed planning (1 newsletter published every 6 months). The newsletter has been distributed to web registered users and has been made public by making all of them available on the project website.

Figure 3-5 - examples of Newsletter published between M18-M24

KPIs analysis

The progress of the key performance indicators for press releases and newsletters perfectly follows the proposed calendar.

Table 3-4: newsletter and press release KPIs evolution and M36 estimation

KPIs	GA	M12	M18	M24	expected M36
# newsletters published	6	1	2	3	6
# press releases published	16	1	4	7	16

No deviations are expected at M36.

It is worth noting that, a part from the newsletters published by ePLANET, project partners have also included ePLANET information in at least 17 other newsletters.

3.4 Stakeholders Forum

Following the strategy defined in WP5, the ePLANET team has organised a set of Stakeholders Forums to increase knowledge amongst project partners, enhance engagement with key stakeholders and fine tune the ongoing ePLANET developments.

While these are not part of the Communication and Dissemination activities, there is an evident link; thus, the summary of these activities is included in this report.

By M24, and following the proposed calendar, 7 out of the envisaged 12 meetings have already been held. Moreover, an additional (smaller) Stakeholders Forum has been organised in the pilot region of Catalonia.

KPIs analysis

Next table shows the key performance indicators for this activity by M24 and M36 estimation based on the proposed timeline.

Table 3-5: Stakeholders Forum KPIs evolution and M36 estimation

KPIs	GA	M12	M18	M24	expected M36
# engaged stakeholders	150	--	110	120	>150

It is not expected any major deviation regarding the final number of engaged stakeholders by M36.

3.5 Webinars and workshops

Webinars and workshops are part of the strategy to build capacities within pilot regions, scale up the project outputs at national level and replicate them at a EU-wide audience. This strategy is developed in Work Packages 4 and 5, which include both public and private webinars and workshops.

Following the proposed timeline, most of the workshops and webinars will be done within the last year of the project, in particular within the 1st semester of the last year. However, some of them have already been realised, with around 150 attendees in total.

The full list of events can be found in the next table:

Table 3-6: list of ePLANET webinars and workshop until M24

date	event	attendees
25.10.22	Workshop. Presentation to mayors of Girona region (Girona, CAT). Partners: CIMNE, DDGI, ICAEN	33
24.4.23	Workshop. Presentation to local authorities from follower region, in the framework of "Municipal challenges towards open innovation and European projects" workshop (Baix Llobregat, CAT). Partners: CIMNE	50
2.5.23	Workshop. CBA to technicians of councils in Girona region. Partners: CIMNE, DDGI.	20
8.6.23	Workshop. CBA in Chania: Chania, Platania, Kantanou-Selinou. Partners: RDFC, CRES, CIMNE.	48
9.6.23	Workshop. CBA in Chania: Minoa Pediadas, Viannos i Arhanes-Asterousia. Partners: RDFC, CRES, CIMNE.	
21.6.23	Webinar. CBA in Heraklion. Partners: RDFC, CIMNE.	
11.7.23	Workshop. CBA in Ierapetra. Partners: RDFC, CRES.	
12.7.23	Workshop. CBA in Rethymnio. Partners: RDFC, CRES.	
13.7.23	Workshop. CBA in Agios Nikolaos. Partners: RDFC, CRES.	

Some examples of the workshops already carried on are included in the following figures.

Figure 3-6 - examples of workshops realised between M18-M24

KPIs analysis

Next table shows the evolution of the main performance indicators until M24.

Table 3-7: webinars and workshops KPIs at M24

KPIs (attendees)	GA	M12	M18	M24	expected M36
user empowerment private webinars	960	--	--	83	--
user empowerment public webinars	720	--	--	--	--
user empowerment private workshops	240	--	--	68	--
scaling-up webinars	720	--	--	--	--
scaling-up workshops	120	--	--	--	--

Most of the webinars and workshops are planned to be deployed between M24 and M30. Thus, the analysis of the indicators at this point can't be conclusive regarding the progress of the activities by M36.

The ePLANET team considers that no major deviations are expected at M36 compared to GA requirements.

3.6 Videos

Communication videos are key to raise awareness on the opportunities of using ePLANET platform and governance strategies, and so attract public authorities on the adoption of ePLANET outcomes.

At the point of writing this report, and following the proposed timeline, only 1 video has been finalised (named "ePLANET constitutional video"). This video -available at the [ePLANET Youtube channel](#)- focuses on the project goals and future outcomes to increase the potential target audience's interest in the project activities.

A part from this constitutional video, the ePLANET team is working on the production of the 3 scaling-up videos, which should emphasise on the added-value of ePLANET tools for local authorities willing to manage energy transition in their territory effectively. Each one of these videos will be tailored to a specific pilot region, including testimonials from that region and the use of the local language. These videos -to be submitted by M24- are already in their final production stage.

Figure 3-7 - Frame of the constitutional video

Figure 3-8 - Frame of the scaling-up videos (still under production)

KPIs analysis

At this point, it is only possible to analyse the progress of the indicators for the 1st video, the constitutional video. Apart from including it on the ePLANET Youtube channel, this constitutional video has also been promoted through Social Media channels, like LinkedIn and Twitter, and the project website, to maximise its visibility.

Next table shows the evolution of the main performance indicators until M24, and the expected values if the 2nd year trend is maintained.

Table 3-8: videos KPIs evolution and M36 estimation

KPIs	GA	M12	M18	M24	expected M36
# views (constitutional video)	1000	103	844	982	>1000
# views (scaling up videos)	1500	--	--	--	--
# views (replication videos)	1000	--	--	--	--

The number of views includes both direct views from Youtube channel and indirect views from social media channels, in particular LinkedIn. The indicators from social media channels are based on the total visualisation time, normalised by the average visualisation time of each “view” in the Youtube channel.

3.7 Conferences and scientific publications

PPs should present ePLANET platform and governance methodology into at least 8 conferences to enlarge the dissemination reach. Moreover, scientific papers will be produced to disseminate the project’s proceedings and results.

By M24, the project has already been presented at different conferences and professional seminars. Below is the list of the different events, with the corresponding attendance.

Table 3-9: List of conferences where ePLANET has been presented

date	event	attendees
11.7.22	Concordia University Summer School (Montreal, CA). Double session (15.07.22). Partners: CIMNE.	50
20.3.23	European Congress of Regional and Local Authorities (?). Partners: DDGI.	20
11.4.23	Working meeting of IEA EBC Annex 83, Positive Energy Districts (Palermo, IT). Partners: CIMNE.	50
28.4.23	ICEEEP23 Congress (Barcelona, CAT). Presentation awarded by the congress. Partners: ICAEN, CIMNE.	40

KPIs analysis

Next table shows the evolution of the main performance indicators until M24.

Table 3-10: website KPIs evolution at M24

KPIs	GA	M12	M18	M24	expected M36
# attendees in conferences	320	50	50	120	--
# attendees at final event	50	--	--	--	--

Most of the conferences will be held within the 3rd year of the project, as all the developments will be already done. The ePLANET team does not expect any major deviation regarding the achievement of these KPIs by the end of the project.

3.8 Site visits

The project activities include 3 site visits (one in each of the pilot regions), which will also be addressed to stakeholders and members of follower regions. All of them will be carried on during the last year of the project; thus at M24 there has not been any relevant activity.

Only some small site visit has been done in the framework of the 3rd project meeting held in Zlín (CZ). In particular, some of the project partners visited the municipality of Hostětín (in Zlín region, CZ), which represents one of the project's use cases.

KPIs analysis

As all the major site visits are to be done between M24 and M36, there are no intermediate targets for the site visit performance indicators.

Table 3-11: site visits KPIs evolution and M36 estimation

KPIs	GA	M12	M18	M24	expected M36
# attendees at site visits	75	6	6	6	75

The project team does not expect any major deviation regarding these indicators.

3.9 Other Communication and Dissemination activities

Project leaflet

The project leaflets have been designed before the proposed timeline, in order to facilitate specific tasks from WP2 and WP4, in particular the ones related to surveys with stakeholders.

Figure 3-9 - First version of ePLANET leaflet (English version)

Launch of the Open Call for Follower Regions

The ePLANET actions include the identification and selection of different follower regions that will benefit from the project outcomes. The whole activity is included in Work Package 5, but the selection procedure has been accompanied by a communication action through the main social channels of the project, together with the creation of a specific page in the ePLANET website.

Figure 3-10 - Open Call section in the ePLANET website

Project brochure (in production stage)

The ePLANET team is working on the production of a project brochure, expected to be publicly available by M24.

While writing this report, the brochure is still unavailable, but some images can already be shown.

Figure 3-11 - Project brochure schemes

4 Conclusions on the progress of ePLANET's C&D activities at M24

Following the detailed analysis of the KPIs per type of activity, it's clear that C&D activities are overall progressing adequately at M24. For example, the number of unique visitors to the ePLANET website, the overall impressions in Twitter channel or the number of attendees in presentations of ePLANET in different conferences.

Only some actions are required to increase the impact of LinkedIn activity, but the ePLANET project team is already working on them and it does not expect any major deviations in achievements by the end of the project (M36).

Next table summarises the progress of the different communication and dissemination activities of the project until M24.

Table 4-1: Progress of Communication and Dissemination activities at M24

Channel	KPIs	Target M36	Target M24	Total M24	[% M24]
Website	# unique visitors	4.000	2.667	2.866	107%
	# visits, monthly average	100	100	336	336%
Twitter	# followers	500	333	387	116%
	#impressions	10.000	6667	21.272	319%
LinkedIn	# members	500	333	262	79%
	#shares	300	200	155	78%
Youtube	# views (constitutional video)	1.000	833	982	118%
	# views (regional videos)	1.500	--	0	
	# views (EU-wide videos)	1.000	--	0	
Newsletter	# publications	6	3	3	100%
PR	# publications	16	7	7	100%
SF	# engaged stakeholders	150	100	120	120%
Webinars & Workshops,	user empowerment private webinars	960	--	83	
	user empowerment public webinars	720	--	0	
	user empowerment private workshops	240	--	68	
	scaling-up webinars	720	--	0	
	scaling-up workshops	120	--	0	
Conferences & events	# attendees in presentations	320	120	160	133%
	# attendees in final event	50	--	0	
Site visits	# attendees	75	--	6	
Additional audience	# additional audience, including partners' social channels, website, newsletters, emails, and other events	--	--	17.431	
	# newsletters from project partners	--	--	17	

